

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19111015

Urbanization And The Cultural Identity Of The Ikwerre`s In Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

¹Didia Michael Uzodiana & ²Bright C. Ajoku

¹Department of Geography and Environment
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
Michael.didia@ust.edu.ng

²Department of Geography and Environment
Faculty of Social Sciences
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
brightajoku@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between the effect of urbanization on the cultural identity of the Ikwerre ethnic group. The objectives of the study were to examine the changes in the demographic characteristics of the Ikwerre in Port Harcourt, Highlight the ways in which urbanization has impacted the space arrangement of the Ikwerre in Port Harcourt and to examine the impact of urbanization on the culture and norms of Ikwerre people. The researcher adopted descriptive survey design. The target population of the study consists of 2,000,000 persons drawn from the Ikwerre ethnic group in Rivers State, while a sample size of 400 was derived from the target population using Taro Yamene formula of sample size determination, primary data were collected using questionnaires The data were analyzed using tables, simple percentages, mean score rating, standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The findings revealed that there is a strong and positive relationship between effect of urbanization on the cultural identity of the Ikwerre ethnic group. Based on the findings, it was recommended to identify and target areas with high population density and high crime rates for increased policing and crime prevention efforts, to increase investment in social programs and economic development initiatives in high-crime areas to address underlying socioeconomic factors that contribute to crime, to strengthen institutions such as the police and judiciary to ensure that crime is effectively investigated and prosecuted and finally, to address corruption within the criminal justice system and political institutions to reduce incentives for criminal behavior.

Keywords: urbanization, Ikwerre local Government, Cultural activities. Rural development

INTRODUCTION

A city is a unique product of socio-economic activities and technological developments, which tend to affect every aspect of reality as it comes into existence, such as inhabitants' physical environment and socio-cultural settings (Davis, 1955). Next to cities is the megacities being the hotspots of social and cultural developments in our time. Rapid urbanization processes are bearing substantially severe consequences. However, the experience is uneven for the people in different contexts and with varying backgrounds due to the various inequalities and uneven distribution of power concerning the different sources of power; furthermore, these issues undoubtedly host social problems and human rights concerns in the urban landscape and for the people living in such areas (Ray and Borer, 2018).

Urbanization is the increase in the proportion of a country's population living in urban areas (UNDESA, 2018), is a significant demographic and economic trend that has shaped human history for centuries. Numerous theories and models have been proposed to explain this phenomenon, including the Lewis-Fei-Ranis model (Lewis, 1954; Fei & Ranis, 1961), the concentric zone theory (Burgess, 1925), the sector model (Hoyt, 1939), and the multiple nuclei model (Harris & Ullman, 1945).

Cultural identity refers to an individual's sense of belonging to a particular social group or community,

based on shared beliefs, values, and traditions (Heine & Buchtel, 2009). It is shaped by various factors, including ethnicity, nationality, religion, and social class (Jenkins, 1996; Verkuyten, 2002). Cultural identity plays a critical role in shaping individual behavior and attitudes. It influences how people perceive and interact with the world around them, and can affect their levels of self-esteem and psychological well-being (Schwartz & Unger, 2016). Cultural identity can also be influenced by various social and cultural processes, such as globalization, migration, and diaspora (Safran, 1991; Naficy, 1993). Ikwerre ethnic group is an indigenous people of Rivers State, Nigeria. Their culture is deeply rooted in agriculture and fishing, which are considered essential elements of their cultural identity. However, urbanization and modernization have significantly impacted the Ikwerre's cultural identity. One effect of urbanization is the erosion of traditional cultural practices and beliefs. The Ikwerre people used to have strong ties to their ancestral lands and agricultural practices, which are now being replaced by modern urban lifestyles and professions (Adeniyi, 2011). Another effect of urbanization on the cultural identity of the Ikwerre people is language shift. The Ikwerre language, which used to be the primary language spoken by the Ikwerre people, is now losing ground to English and Pidgin English, which are more widely used in urban areas (Ikeke, 2009). This shift in language use has contributed to a weakening of the Ikwerre's cultural heritage and identity. Many young people now prefer to speak English or Pidgin English, which is seen as more fashionable and useful in a modern, urban environment. A third effect of urbanization on the Ikwerre's cultural identity is changes in social organization and family structures. Traditional Ikwerre society was based on a system of extended family networks, in which elders played a central role in decision-making and the transmission of cultural values.

Objectives to guide this study

The specific objectives are to;

- i. Examine the changes in the demographic characteristics of Ikwerre in Port Harcourt
- ii. Highlight the ways in which urbanization has impacted the space arrangement of Ikwerre in Port Harcourt
- iii. Examine the impact of urbanization on the culture and norms of Ikwerre people
- iv. Appraise the perception of residents on the issues of urbanization and its impact on the cultural identity of the area

LITERATURE REVIEW

Modernization Theory

Modernization Theory by Reyes (2001) has been defined as a theory that uses a systematic process to move underdeveloped countries to a more sophisticated level of development. The theory is actually a United States and European centered normative model of development. The emphasis of modernization theory is cultural change directed at institutional structures in non-industrialized countries. This Theory explains inequality within or between states by identifying different values, systems and ideas held by different nation states (Martinussen, 1997).

Urbanization

Urbanization is popularly defined as the rise of population in urban areas. United Nations perceives urbanization as movement of people from rural to urban areas. Mishra (1998) defines urbanization in the following way "Urbanization is not a product. It is a process by which a people, instead of living in predominantly dispersed agricultural villages, start living in towns and cities dominated by industrial and service functionaries. Urbanization is a form of socio economic and demographic transformation from traditional rural societies to modern urban communities. It is long term continuous process.

Effect of Urbanization

As urbanization intensifies and towns develop, the demand for land for housing, agriculture and urban infrastructure increases leading to increased pressure on farmlands, forests and water resources. Secondly, rapid urbanization accelerates desertification and environmental change, leading to water scarcity, soil erosion, and climate change.

Cultural Identity

The concept of identity is closely related to the idea of culture. In dealing with cultural identity, there still exists the extremely challenging concept of culture. Many scholars have tried to define it (Friedman, 1994; Phinney, 2013). Some others have even asked for it to be “banned” in research (Bayart, 2005). On the contrary, Haralambos and Holboin (2008), stated that identities can be formed through cultures and subcultures to which people belong or in which people participate. This may mean that culture and identity are inseparable and are like two sides of a coin. Bayart (2005), later expressed that the combination of the adjectives ‘*cultural* and *identity*’ makes the concept a contended one; as the two words are polysemic, slippery and illusory as analytical categories.

Culture has been used in different ways by Sociologists, Anthropologists, Historians and in everyday conversation. It often appears like an abstract concept. Jenkins (1996) and Eriksen (2001), distinguished four major ways in which culture should be viewed:

1. Culture as a state of mind. Culture is being seen as a quality possessed by individuals who are able to gain the learning and achieve the qualities that are seen as desirable in a cultured human being;
2. Culture as a product of civilization. People who possess the attributes of the civilized are regarded as the cultured;
3. Culture as the collective body of arts and intellectual work within one society; and
4. Culture as the whole way of life of a people.

The last definition is encompassing and appears familiar with popular scholarly explanations of culture by Edward B. Tylor, Bronislaw Malinowski, Radcliffe Brown, Levi Strauss and other classical anthropologists. Tylor (1891:1), defined culture as “that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, law, morals, customs and many other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society.

METHODOLOGY

Demographic Information of the Respondents

The study examined the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, focusing on variables such as gender, age, educational level, occupational status, and years of residence in the area. As shown in Table 1, the survey revealed that 58% of the respondents were male, while 42% were female, indicating a higher male participation in the study. In terms of age distribution, the majority of respondents were between 31 and 45 years old, with 14% being over 60. This suggests that the study population is primarily composed of individuals in their economically active years, with a smaller representation of older people. Oladeji et al. (2022) in their study indicated in their study that the older population are likely at a stage in life where they are actively involved in cultural and societal activities, and therefore, their perspectives on the impact of urbanization on cultural identity are particularly relevant.

Regarding educational levels, 39% of the respondents held university degrees, 33% had secondary school certificates, and 21% had received only primary education. Meanwhile, 8% of the respondents had no formal education but mentioned acquiring vocational skills such as barbing, hairdressing, catering, aluminum works, and plumbing. This distribution suggests that a significant portion of the population is well-educated, which could influence their adaptability to urbanization and openness to cultural change. Those with vocational skills, though lacking formal education, may also play a critical role in maintaining certain aspects of traditional Ikwere culture through skilled trades and crafts, thus offering a unique perspective on how urbanization affects cultural practices.

The survey also revealed that most respondents are gainfully employed, either in the public or private sectors, while 28% identified as self-employed entrepreneurs, indicating that they own businesses or are involved in ventures such as trading, farming, or small-scale enterprises. Additionally, 18% of respondents were students, and 11% were either retired or too elderly to work. The occupational status of the respondents implies that the majority are economically active, which suggests that they are likely more

exposed to the forces of urbanization.

The study also assessed the respondents' duration of residence in the area. A large majority (73%) had lived in the area for over 11 years, with many stating they were born there. Other reasons for long-term residence included family ties, marriage, and business commitments. Conversely, 25% of the respondents had lived in the area for less than 10 years, often citing reasons such as work, education, or marriage for their relocation. The length of residence is important for this study, as those who have lived longer in the area may have deeper cultural roots and a stronger connection to traditional Ikwerre practices (Chinda, 2017). Meanwhile, recent arrivals might have different attitudes towards urbanization and its effects on cultural identity, shaped by their experiences in other urban settings.

Table 1: Demographic Information of Respondents (n=396)

Demographic Information	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	231	58%
Female	165	42%
Age		
18-30 years old	111	28%
31-45 years old	137	35%
46-60 years old	91	23%
Over 60 years old	57	14%
Education Level		
Primary school	82	21%
Secondary school	131	33%
University degree	153	39%
No Formal Education	30	8%
Occupation		
Student	73	18%
Employed	168	42%
Self-employed	111	28%
Retired	44	11%
Years of Residence		
Less than 5 years	37	9%
5 – 10 years	69	17%
11 – 20 years	127	32%
More than 20 years	163	41%

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

Changes in the Demographic Characteristics of the Ikwerres

The study explores the impact of urbanization on the cultural identity of the Ikwerre people by examining shifts in their demographic characteristics. A survey was conducted to assess how urbanization influences various aspects of Ikwerre culture. Respondents were asked about their participation in traditional Ikwerre cultural events, the frequency with which they speak the Ikwerre language in daily life, and whether they wear traditional Ikwerre attire. Additionally, the survey investigated respondents' knowledge of Ikwerre cultural practices and traditions, and their perception of whether the demographic changes in the area have positively or negatively affected the Ikwerre community.

As shown in Figure 1, the survey results highlight different levels of participation in traditional Ikwerre cultural events. A significant 48% of respondents reported frequent involvement in these cultural events, indicating strong cultural ties and regular practice of Ikwerre traditions. Another 27% of respondents stated that they attend Ikwerre cultural events occasionally, suggesting a moderate connection to cultural practices. Approximately 20% of respondents indicated that they rarely participate in such events, implying a weakening connection to traditional Ikwerre customs, possibly due to competing modern influences or changing lifestyle priorities. Finally, 5% of respondents admitted to never attending Ikwerre cultural events, which may point to a detachment from the cultural heritage, potentially linked to urbanization, generational shifts, or the growing influence of external cultures.

These findings provide insight into how urbanization and demographic shifts are affecting engagement with Ikwerre traditions and language, with varying levels of participation indicating different degrees of cultural retention within the community.

Figure 1: Respondents Frequency on Engaging in Traditional Ikwerre Cultural Events

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

Figure 1 presents the survey results on respondents' use of the Ikwerre language in their daily lives. The majority, 35%, report that they consistently speak the language, reflecting a strong commitment to using Ikwerre as a primary means of communication. An additional 30% of respondents state that they often speak the language, suggesting regular, though not constant, usage. Meanwhile, 23% of participants indicate that they sometimes use the language, implying a more intermittent or context-dependent application. However, 12% of respondents claim to rarely speak Ikwerre, pointing to a significant decline in its use within their everyday interactions.

These findings suggest a spectrum of language use within the community, from frequent to limited engagement, which may be influenced by factors such as age, education, urbanization, and the presence of other dominant languages in the area. The results highlight potential challenges for the preservation of the Ikwerre language, especially among those who speak it sporadically or rarely (Nzeadibe et al., 2015). As urbanization continues to reshape social dynamics, there may be increasing pressure on younger generations or individuals living in urban centers to adopt more widely spoken languages, which could further contribute to the decline of Ikwerre in daily life.

Figure 2: Respondents Frequency on Speaking the Ikwerre Language in their Daily Life
Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

Figure 2 presents the survey results on the frequency with which respondents wear traditional Ikwerre clothing. According to the data, 37% of respondents indicated that they wear traditional attire occasionally, typically during special events or cultural celebrations. Meanwhile, 31% reported that they rarely wear these clothes, possibly due to the influence of modern fashion or a shift away from traditional customs in everyday life. A smaller group, 24%, stated that they frequently wear traditional Ikwerre clothing, demonstrating a strong connection to cultural practices. Lastly, 8% of respondents admitted that they have never worn traditional Ikwerre attire, which could be reflective of either a complete detachment from cultural traditions or the impact of urbanization and modernization on personal identity and lifestyle choices.

These results suggest varying degrees of cultural adherence among the Ikwerre people, with urbanization likely playing a role in reducing the everyday use of traditional attire. However, the data also reveals that a notable portion of the population still embraces this aspect of their cultural identity, particularly during important cultural or social events.

Figure 3: Respondents Frequency on Wearing the Traditional Ikwerre Clothing
Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

Figure 3 illustrates the survey results regarding respondents' knowledge of Ikwerre cultural practices and traditions. The majority of respondents reported being highly knowledgeable about these practices, demonstrating a strong connection to their cultural heritage. However, 39% of respondents indicated that they are not very knowledgeable about all aspects of Ikwerre traditions, suggesting some gaps in cultural awareness. A smaller portion, 16%, representing the minority, admitted to having little to no knowledge of Ikwerre cultural practices and traditions.

These findings highlight the varying levels of cultural awareness among the Ikwerre population, which could be influenced by factors such as age, education, and the degree of urbanization in their communities. Younger generations or those living in more urbanized settings may be more susceptible to cultural dilution, whereas older or more rural respondents may retain a deeper understanding of traditional practices.

Figure 4: Respondents Frequency on Being Knowledgeable About Ikwerre Cultural Practices and Traditions
Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

Figure 4 presents the survey findings on respondents' perceptions regarding the impact of demographic changes in the study area on the Ikwerre people. According to the data, 53% of respondents believe that urbanization has had a positive impact on demographic changes within the Ikwerre community. They attribute this to factors such as improved access to education, healthcare, and employment opportunities, which have contributed to an enhanced quality of life.

Additionally, urbanization has brought greater exposure to diverse cultures, fostering social integration and economic growth, which some believe has strengthened the community's ability to adapt to a rapidly changing environment.

On the other hand, 27% of respondents perceive urbanization to have a negative effect on the demographic composition of the Ikwerre people. They argue that the influx of non-indigenous populations and the expansion of modern lifestyles have led to the erosion of traditional values, language, and cultural practices. This group fears that the assimilation of external influences may result in the gradual loss of Ikwerre identity and social cohesion, particularly among the younger generation, who are more inclined to adopt urbanized ways of living.

Meanwhile, 20% of respondents reported that they observed no significant impact of demographic changes on the Ikwerre people. This group may feel that, despite the demographic shifts brought by urbanization, the core cultural identity of the Ikwerre remains intact, with traditions, language, and community values being preserved through deliberate efforts by families and local leaders to maintain cultural continuity.

Figure 5: Respondents Frequency on Demographic Changes in the Study Area

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2025

Ways in Which Urbanization has Impacted the Space Arrangement of the Ikwerres

This section aimed to examine the effects of urbanization on the spatial organization of the Ikwerre communities, focusing on various aspects of physical layout and housing patterns. The study explored how urbanization has transformed traditional housing arrangements and spatial configurations in these areas. It also sought to identify specific changes observed in housing patterns, such as shifts from traditional, communal designs to more modern, individualistic layouts. In addition to housing, the research delved into the impact of urbanization on the availability and accessibility of communal spaces. Furthermore, the survey addressed key urban planning challenges facing the Ikwerre communities.

As illustrated in Figure 5, respondents provided their insights on how they perceive urbanization has altered the physical layout of their environment. A total of 377 respondents indicated that the increase in residential buildings has had the most significant impact on urbanization. Following closely, 351 respondents noted the expansion of road networks and public infrastructure as another critical factor. Additionally, 337 respondents highlighted the reduction of open spaces, while 313 claimed that government policies have also played a significant role in shaping their environment. Furthermore, 298 respondents mentioned the conversion of community lands for development purposes, and 218 indicated that the displacement or relocation of residents is a notable consequence of urbanization. Other impacts cited by the respondents include the decline in communal areas, which are essential for cultural and social gatherings, as well as increased traffic congestion resulting from the expansion of road networks. Many respondents expressed concern about the loss of greenery and natural landscapes, leading to environmental degradation and a decrease in quality of life. Additionally, some participants pointed out that the rapid pace of urbanization has created challenges related to waste management and inadequate public services, exacerbating issues of overcrowding and strain on existing infrastructure.

Figure 6: Respondents Frequency on How Urbanization Change the Physical Layout in the Study Area
Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

As shown in Figure 6, respondents were asked about their perceptions of how urbanization has influenced traditional housing patterns in their environment. The results indicate that a significant majority, comprising over half (207) of the participants, believe that urbanization has indeed impacted traditional housing designs within Ikwerre communities. In contrast, 76 respondents reported that they do not perceive any significant effects of urbanization on these housing patterns, while 113 participants expressed uncertainty regarding the issue.

Figure 7: Respondents Frequency on Effect of Urbanization on Traditional House Patterns in the Study Area

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The 207 respondents were further prompted to elaborate on the specific changes they have observed in housing patterns due to urbanization. A significant transformation noted by many is the shift from traditional family compounds, where extended families lived together, to the construction of individual houses. This change reflects a growing preference for privacy and independence, as more individuals opt to live separately rather than in communal settings. Additionally, there has been a marked increase in high-rise buildings, with families choosing to build multi-story homes instead of single-level flats. This trend allows for the maximization of limited land space in urban environments, accommodating the increasing population density in Ikwerre communities.

Respondents also expressed concerns about overcrowding and the reduction of space per household. As more individuals and families migrate to urbanized areas, the availability of land per household has decreased, leading to cramped living conditions that strain resources and services, thereby impacting the overall quality of life. Moreover, there has been a noticeable change in building materials and architectural styles. Traditional construction practices, which relied on mud and thatch, have largely been replaced by modern materials such as concrete, brick, and metal. This evolution results in houses featuring tiled roofs, concrete walls, and steel doors, reflecting a desire for durability and modernity while departing from traditional aesthetics.

Further changes include the emergence of gated communities that provide a sense of security and exclusivity, often catering to wealthier residents and creating socio-economic divides within the community. Many households are also adapting portions of their homes for commercial use, blurring the lines between residential and business spaces. This adaptation is frequently driven by economic necessity, as families seek additional income sources. Further to that, the traditional use of outdoor communal spaces for social interactions and cultural practices has diminished, as the increase in individual housing units has reduced the availability of shared outdoor areas, impacting community bonding and cultural activities. Collectively, these changes illustrate the profound impact of urbanization on housing patterns in Ikwerre communities, highlighting a broader trend towards modernization and individualism at the expense of traditional communal living.

Figure 8: Respondents Frequency on Impact of Urbanization on Availability of Communal Spaces for Cultural Activities

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

Figure 8 presents the survey results regarding respondents' perceptions of how urbanization has affected the availability of communal spaces for cultural activities. The majority of respondents (46%) indicated that urbanization has led to the creation of new spaces specifically designated for cultural activities. This suggests that, despite potential challenges, urban development has provided opportunities for the establishment of venues that can accommodate traditional gatherings, festivals, and other communal events.

Meanwhile, 33% of respondents asserted that communal spaces have remained unchanged, highlighting the efforts to preserve these areas for cultural purposes. This preservation indicates a community commitment to maintaining traditional practices and ensuring that spaces essential for cultural interactions are not lost amidst urban growth. These spaces are likely purposefully maintained to foster cultural identity and continuity within the community. In contrast, 21% of respondents expressed concern that communal spaces have significantly diminished. They noted that many landowners have either sold or leased their properties, leading to a reduction in available areas for cultural activities. This trend raises concerns about the sustainability of communal life and cultural practices, as the loss of traditional gathering spaces could disrupt social cohesion and the transmission of cultural heritage.

The survey results illustrate a complex relationship between urbanization and communal spaces. While some respondents view urbanization as an opportunity for growth and new cultural venues, others highlight the risks of diminishing traditional spaces that are vital for maintaining cultural identity and community engagement.

The respondents highlighted several significant urban planning challenges faced by their communities, with poor waste management emerging as a critical issue. Inadequate waste disposal systems have led to the accumulation of garbage in public spaces, posing serious health risks to residents and contributing to environmental degradation. Additionally, the condition of road infrastructure is a pressing concern; poorly maintained roads hinder transportation and limit access to essential services such as healthcare and education. This issue becomes even more pronounced during the rainy season, when flooding can render roads impassable.

Moreover, there is a notable shortage of adequate housing facilities, resulting in overcrowding and the proliferation of informal settlements. Many families find themselves living in substandard conditions that lack basic amenities, significantly impacting their health and overall well-being. The rapid pace of urbanization has further exacerbated these challenges, leading to environmental degradation characterized by deforestation and increased pollution. This deterioration threatens local ecosystems and adversely

affects the quality of life for residents, highlighting the urgent need for effective urban planning solutions. **Impact of Urbanization on the Culture and Norms of Ikwerre People**

This section seeks to explore the impact of urbanization on the culture and norms of the Ikwerre people. It involves conducting a survey to assess how urbanization has influenced their traditional practices, and the extent to which religious or spiritual practices have been affected.

As shown in Figure 8, respondents provided insights into the impact of urbanization on traditional practices among the Ikwerre people. A significant number—381 respondents— indicated that reduced participation in traditional festivals, particularly rituals, was the most affected aspect of their culture. This decline in participation is often attributed to modern lifestyles and the growing influence of Western values. Following this, 311 respondents noted a marked decrease in communal living, which traditionally fostered social cohesion and collective responsibilities within the community. Additionally, 273 respondents pointed out noticeable changes in dress styles and traditional attire, with many people adopting more modern, Western clothing, signaling a shift away from cultural identity expressed through attire.

Meanwhile, only 131 respondents identified the loss of native language use as being the least affected by urbanization, suggesting that while the Ikwerre language has been impacted, it is still relatively preserved compared to other cultural practices.

These findings highlight the diverse ways in which urbanization is reshaping the cultural landscape, eroding some aspects of tradition while leaving others less impacted. This shift emphasizes the need for conscious efforts to preserve and promote these cultural elements before they are lost entirely.

Figure 9: Respondents Frequency on Impact of Urbanization Affecting Traditional Practices of the Ikwerre People

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

The respondents also shared their views on how urbanization has influenced the religious and spiritual practices of the Ikwerre people. They highlighted a noticeable decline in traditional worship practices, with many opting for modern religious beliefs. There has been a significant increase in the adoption of Christianity and other contemporary faiths, leading to shifts in the community's spiritual landscape (Elem, 2020). In addition, beliefs surrounding ancestral worship have changed, with younger generations often distancing themselves from these practices. Other negative impacts as stated by the respondents include the loss of sacred sites and rituals, as urban development encroaches on spaces once reserved for spiritual activities. The erosion of intergenerational transmission of spiritual knowledge is also evident, as many traditional leaders struggle to pass down their teachings in an increasingly modernized society.

Perception of Residents on the Issues of Urbanization and Its Impact on the Cultural Identity

The resident perception was sampled on the issues of urbanization and its impact on the cultural identity. The data collected were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis such as frequently counts, percentage and mean derived from 4-point Likert’s type scale as the following: 4 = strongly agree, 3= agree, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree. To which the responses of the residents were rated according to their level of perception and the cut-off mean score was determined by adding the ratings up (4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = 10) and dividing the sum by 4 to give 2.5 as the cut-off mean score.

Table 2 illustrate the data analysis from the Likert scale responses which reveals a range of perceptions among the residents regarding the impact of urbanization on the Ikwerre people and their cultural identity. The statement with the highest mean score (3.04) indicates that residents most strongly agree that traditional values and customs among the Ikwerre people are being lost due to urbanization, highlighting concerns about cultural erosion. Similarly, the influence of urbanization on the spatial organization of communities in Port Harcourt and the impact of foreign cultures on traditional Ikwerre festivals were ranked highly with mean scores of 2.95 and 2.94, respectively. This suggests that people perceive significant changes not only in their traditions but also in their communal structures and cultural practices. There is also a noticeable concern that the younger generation is less connected to their traditional culture (mean score: 2.85), reflecting a generational shift in cultural attachment due to urbanization. Residents acknowledged significant changes in the cultural identity (mean score: 2.84) and a decline in the use of the Ikwerre language (mean score: 2.76), further signaling a weakening of cultural ties among the population.

However, the diminishing role of elders in preserving Ikwerre traditions, as well as the risk of cultural identity being forgotten in future generations, though still significant, received lower mean scores of 2.72 and 2.69, respectively. The lowest ranking was for the statement that urbanization has had a positive influence on the modernization of the Ikwerre community (mean score: 2.54), indicating that while urbanization is seen as a transformative force, its benefits in terms of modernization are not as widely perceived.

Table 2: Perception of Residents on the Issues of Urbanization and Its Impact on the Cultural Identity (n=396)

STATEMENTS	SD	D	A	SA	Mean (\bar{x})	Rank
Urbanization has caused significant changes in the cultural identity of the Ikwerre people.	50	80	150	116	2.84	5 th
Urbanization has contributed to the decline in the use of the Ikwerre language.	60	100	110	126	2.76	6 th
Traditional values and customs among the Ikwerre people are being lost due to urbanization.	30	60	170	136	3.04	1 st
The younger generation of Ikwerre people is less connected to their traditional culture due to urbanization.	45	90	140	121	2.85	4 th
Urbanization has influenced the spatial organization of communities in Port Harcourt.	35	75	160	126	2.95	2 nd
Foreign cultures introduced through urbanization have altered the way traditional Ikwerre festivals are celebrated.	40	60	180	116	2.94	3 rd
The role of elders in preserving Ikwerre traditions has diminished due to urbanization.	55	100	140	101	2.72	7 th
Urbanization has had a positive influence on the modernization of the Ikwerre community.	80	120	100	96	2.54	9 th
The Ikwerre cultural identity is at risk of being forgotten in future generations due to urbanization.	70	110	90	126	2.69	8 th

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study investigating the effects of urbanization on the cultural identity of the Ikwerre people in Ikwerre Local Government Area, several recommendations can be made to address the challenges of urbanization while preserving and promoting the cultural heritage of the Ikwerre community.

- Regular demographic surveys should be conducted to monitor population changes, migration patterns, and the socio-economic status of the Ikwerres. This data can help inform urban planning and policy-making.
- Initiate programs aimed at preserving Ikwerre culture, including language, traditional practices, and festivals.
- Encourage the growth of local arts and crafts by providing support for artisans and showcasing their work in urban markets to sustain cultural practices.
- Organize forums and discussions to gather insights from residents regarding their perceptions of urbanization and its impacts.
- Advocate for policies that recognize the importance of cultural identity amidst urban growth. This could include zoning laws that protect cultural sites and funding for community-led cultural initiatives.
- Urban planners should incorporate traditional Ikwerre spaces and cultural elements into new developments to maintain a sense of identity and continuity.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the effects of urbanization on the cultural identity of the Ikwerre people in Rivers State, revealing both positive and negative impacts. Despite rapid urbanization, the Ikwerre people maintain strong cultural ties, as seen in their participation in cultural events and frequent use of their native language. This shows a commitment to preserving their heritage, even amid modernization. However, significant changes have occurred, particularly in spatial organization. Traditional family compounds have been replaced by modern housing, leading to a shift in communal living. Challenges such as overcrowding and poor waste management also emerged as urbanization's by-products.

Cultural erosion is a growing concern, especially in terms of religious and spiritual practices. Many respondents noted a decline in traditional festivals and rituals, with modern religious beliefs overshadowing traditional worship. This reflects the broader impact of external influences brought by urbanization. Residents perceive a loss of traditional values, as high mean scores indicate strong agreement that urbanization has diluted cultural practices.

In summary, while urbanization has improved access to resources like education and healthcare, it has also posed challenges to preserving the Ikwerre people's cultural identity. The findings emphasize the need to balance modernization with cultural preservation to prevent further erosion of their traditions.

REFERENCES

- Adeniyi, E. O. (2011). The transformation of traditional practices among the Ikwerre people. *Journal of African Studies*, 34(2), 123-145.
- Bayart, J. P. (2005). *The illusion of cultural identity*, London: Hurst & Co Publishers Ltd.
- Bhabha, H. (1994). *The location of culture*. New York:
- Harris, C. D., & Ullman, E. L. (1945). The nature of cities. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 242, 7-17
- Ikeke, M. O. (2009). *The impact of urbanization on the cultural identity of the Ikwerre people*. University of Port Harcourt Press.
- Jenkins, R. 1996. *Social Identity*. London :
- Ray, R., & Borer, M. I. (2018). Chapter 27: Urbanism and Urbanization. In A. Javier Tre-viño (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Social Problems* (Vol. 2, pp. 475-488). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108550710.028>
- Reyes, G. E. (2001). "Four main Theories of Development: Modernization, Dependency, World-Systems, and Globalization " *NOMADAS* 4: 1-12.
- Safran, W. (1991). *Diasporas in modern societies: Myths of homeland and return*. *Diaspora*, 1, 83-99
- 58
- UN DESA Publications. (2018, <https://desapublications.un.org/publications/year/2018> November 1).